

IMPACT OF TEACHERS' QUALITY AND TEACHING EXPERIENCE ON SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN MATHEMATICS IN OYO TOWN, NIGERIA

BY

FADARE Andrew Ojo¹ & SABITU Kamoru Abiodun²

¹Department of Mathematics, School of Secondary Education (Science Programmes),
Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo, Nigeria

²Department of Science Education, School of General Studies Education, Federal College of Education (Special),
Oyo, Nigeria

ORCID: <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-8727-1676>

Email: sabitu.kamoru1984@fcesoyo.edu.ng

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20964687>

Abstract

This study investigated the impact of teacher's quality and teaching experience on students' academic performance in Mathematics in Oyo town secondary schools. The study adopted a descriptive research design. The population and sample for this study consisted of the one hundred and seventy-three (173) Mathematics teachers in the four (4) Local Government Areas that constituted Oyo town. A Researchers' self-structured questionnaire titled Questionnaire on "Impact of Teachers' Quality and Teaching Experience (QIRQTE)" which was validated by two experts in the field of measurement was used to elicit information from the respondents. Reliability coefficient of 0.88 was obtained using test re-test method. Questionnaires retrieved were collated and analyzed using regression analysis at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that there is significant impact of teachers' quality on students' performance in Mathematics in secondary school in Oyo Town, there is also a significant impact of teachers' teaching experience on students' performance in Mathematics in secondary school in within Oyo in Oyo State, Nigeria, and teachers' quality and teaching experience were taken together jointly predict students' academic performance. Sequel to the findings, it was recommended among others that periodic training and retraining workshops should be organized for teachers to enhance their subject matter knowledge and pedagogical skills by government and they should be encouraged to pursue professional certifications and advanced degrees.

Keywords: Teachers' Quality, Teaching Experience, Secondary School Students, Academic Performance and Mathematics

Introduction

In secondary schools, Mathematics is a fundamental subject that is essential to students' academic and professional opportunities. However, Nigerian students' ability in Mathematics has raised great concerns. It is possible that humans' efforts to resolve some quantitative issues from everyday life were available where Mathematics first emerged. Different definitions and perspectives on Mathematics have been stated today (Tella, 2024). According to Oyedeji (2020), it is a process, a tool, an art, and an innovative language. Mathematics Education is essential in

contemporary education as it significantly influences cognitive development and future opportunities for individuals. Mathematics is a foundational subject that supports several disciplines, including Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) subjects (Weiner, 2022). The importance of Mathematics education cannot be overstated, as it provides students with the skills and knowledge necessary to succeed in an increasingly complex and technological world. Mathematics is composed of sequential rules and cognitive capacities (Usman & Sabitu, 2025). This suggests that there are always necessary steps to take when attempting to

acquire knowledge of intellectual talents for any topic or subject matter in Mathematics. Attempts to exclude crucial mathematical skills can have negative effects because they create gaps in students' understanding of the skills, which hampers their capacity to solve problems (Daso, 2023). The concepts of number and magnitude that provided the foundation for much of that is now known as Mathematics. As a result, Mathematics has come to be known as the science of quantity and space, which is essential to all other technological and scientific fields (Tella, 2024).

Every educational institution employs both internal and external examinations to evaluate its students' academic performance. Teachers have been found to have a significant impact on students' academic performance as well as play an essential part in educational attachment because they are ultimately in control of implementing policies into practice and using concepts based on practice when interacting with students. According to Weiner (2022), assessments of performance shed light on someone's capacity for handling materials rather than symbols. Then, a student's observable and quantifiable conduct during certain situations might be considered based on his/her performance in school. For instance, a student's academic performance in civic education comprises his observable and quantifiable behaviour throughout the course. Individual's scores at any given time from a teacher-made test or a standardized test contribute to academic performance.

Academic performance could be described as the scholastic standing of a student at a given examination. According to Usman and Sabitu, 2025, the scholastic standing could be explained as the grades obtained in a course or group of courses taken. This assertion is consistent with the National Policy on

Education (2014), which defines academic performance as an individual's or an animal's identifiable and quantifiable behavior in a particular environment, typically an experiment. A teacher-made test or a standardized accomplishment test designed for school subject matter can be utilized for assessing academic performance, which is the feature of conduct that can be observed at specific times (Ali, et. al., 2020).

Teachers have been crucial to the teaching and learning process. There is no denying of the fact that the teacher's crucial role in teaching is *Sine qua non*. Teachers' techniques in the classroom are greatly influenced by them. There are actually two types of science educators in Nigerian schools (Nwachuckwu, 2022). The first group consists of educators and teachers with the necessary professional qualifications who are not well-versed in the subject matter of science, while the second group consists of those who are competent in the subject but lack professional training. It follows that the majority of science teachers in practice lack the necessary training. Because science is a dynamic subject, science teachers must receive consistent training and retraining in order to stay up to speed on the latest developments in the field and to be able to effectively impact students' scientific knowledge. Because no educational system is able to surpass the caliber of its instructors.

Teacher quality is hardly defined. The literature on teacher quality shows a wide range of qualifications, characteristics, practices, and outcomes and analyzed their relationships with students learning (Nwachuckwu, 2022). Despite a huge emphasis on teacher quality, educators and policymakers often disagree over the definition of teacher quality, how it should be evaluated and how it should be interpreted and used. One reason to explain this disagreement is that

teacher quality is defined differently for different purposes. For example, the indicators of quality relevant to hiring decisions are different from the indicators used in granting tenure or identifying support needs. Teacher quality is a complex phenomenon for which no general and absolute agreement exists concerning an appropriate and comprehensive definition. Two areas typically have been considered by researchers and policymakers as candidates for describing teacher quality: (a) teacher inputs including teacher characteristics, professional preparation, and license and (b) classroom effectiveness, frequently measured in terms of student performance on standardized tests (Piaro, 2024). Reference recommended the use of teacher quality framework in defining teacher quality. The framework includes two inputs (teacher qualifications and teacher characteristics), a process measure (teacher practices) and an outcome measure (teacher effectiveness).

Research on the quality of educators and how it impacts student academic performance in schools has increased significantly in recent years. However, students' performance is seen as a valid metric and the foundation for a value-added teacher assessment system due to increasing demands on students' accountability (Adaramola & Obomamu, 2018). As consequently, raising the caliber of teachers has been seen as an effective approach for increasing student performance (Piaro, 2024). The results of several studies also show that the reasons behind students' falling academic performance are complex and that stakeholders do not seem to have an opinion on who is to blame (Asikhia, 2020).

According to a study conducted in Kwara State, students' academic performance had been significantly affected by Teacher's capacity building, classroom management,

methodology, personality, and discipline (Adebayo & Sayaya, 2023). Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that students' academic performance is significantly and favourably impacted by teacher's qualification, subject specialization, and time management (Akpo & Jita, 2023). On the contrary, a study conducted in Kenya found that compensation, age, and training had a stronger connection with pupil performance in school than teachers' qualifications and experience (Lydia & Joash, 2024; Agwanda, 2025). The study is in tandem with social cognitive theory by Albert Bandura which suggests that teacher's beliefs in their abilities to impact students' performance.

According to Patrick (2025), researchers and academics usually concur that school factors, such as teacher's qualities, have a greater impact on the academic success than other factors. Nonetheless, there has been disagreement on the significance of particular teacher-related characteristics, which has led to the widespread belief that the empirical data currently available does not indicate that instructors have a significant impact in determining students' academic success.

Teaching experience includes participation in professional development activities geared towards equipping the teacher for better service delivery. Patrick (2025) defined experienced teacher as those who have taught for many years (five year and above) and are able to motivate students and hold their attention, know how they manage their lesson, classroom effectively and can change cause in the middle of a lesson. (Piaro, 2024) believed that greater teaching experience will produce students with greater academic performance.

This study therefore examined the impact of teachers' quality and teaching experience on students' academic performance in

Mathematics in secondary school in Oyo town, Oyo State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The academic performance of secondary school students in Mathematics in Oyo town has been a concern for educators and stakeholders. Despite efforts to improve teaching and learning outcomes, students' achievement in Mathematics remains unsatisfactory. While various factors contribute to this trend, the quality of teachers and their teaching experience are crucial determinants of student academic performance. However, there is a dearth of research on how these factors specifically impact Mathematics education in Oyo town. This study investigates the impact of teacher quality and teaching experience on secondary school students' academic performance in Mathematics in Oyo town, with a view to providing insights for improving Mathematics education

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to examine the impact of teachers' quality and teaching experience on secondary school students' performance in Mathematics in Oyo town. Specifically, it sought to determine if;

1. teachers' quality has impact on students' academic performance in Mathematics in secondary school in Oyo Town.
2. teachers' teaching experience has impact on students' academic performance in Mathematics in secondary school in Oyo town.
3. there will be combine impact of impact of teachers' quality and teaching experience on students' academic performance in Mathematics in secondary school in Oyo Town.

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant impact of teachers' quality on students' academic performance in Mathematics in secondary school in Oyo Town.

H₀₂: There is no significant impact of teachers' teaching experience on students' academic performance in Mathematics in secondary school in Oyo Town.

H₀₃: There is no significant combine impact of impact of teachers' quality and teaching experience on students' academic performance in Mathematics in secondary school in Oyo

Research Method

The study adopted a descriptive research design. This research design was adopted because it provides the opportunity for full, rich and deep descriptions of the participants' perceptions. The population for this study consisted of one hundred and seventy-three (173) Mathematics teachers in the four (4) Local Government Areas that that constituted Oyo Town, namely: Afijio, Atiba, Oyo East and Oyo West Local Government Areas. Total enumeration of the population made the sample size. Researchers' self-structured Questionnaire titled "Questionnaire on Impact of Teachers' Quality and Teaching Experience (QIRQTE)" which was validated by two experts in the field of measurement was used to gather information from the respondents.

The questionnaire consisted of three (3) sections. Section A focuses on the demographic information of the respondents, section B consists questions on impact of teachers' quality on academic performance in Mathematics, section C consists of questions on impact of teachers teaching experience students' academic performance in Mathematics, A modified four-point Likert Scale was adopted for the questions in the questionnaire and were graded as follow: SA=Strongly Agreed, A=Agreed, D=Disagreed and SD=Strongly Disagreed.

The instrument was administered on 20 Mathematics teachers in Ibadan town which is outside the population for the study to obtain a reliability coefficient of 0.88 using a test retest method in a space of one month. The mathematics teachers were briefed of the purpose of the study before administering the instrument. One hundred and seventy-three (173) questionnaires were distributed to the mathematics teachers and strictly monitored by research assistants picked from each schools.

The 173 questionnaires were retrieved, collated and analysed using regression analysis at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

The results were arranged according to the stated hypotheses as follow:

H₀1: There is no significant impact of teachers’ quality on students’ performance in Mathematics in secondary school in Oyo Town.

Table 1: Summary of Linear Regression Analysis Showing the teachers’ quality on students’ performance in Mathematics in secondary school in Oyo Town

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1587.462	1	1587.462	122.216	.000
	Residual	2234.259	172	12.989		
	Total	3821.721	173			

a. Dependent Variable: performance,

b. Predictors: (Constant), teachers’ quality

From the table above, since significance value $p < 0.05$, the null hypothesis that there is no significant impact of teachers’ quality on students’ performance in Mathematics in secondary school in Oyo Town was rejected.

H₀2: There is no significant impact of teachers’ teaching experience on students’ performance in Mathematics in secondary school in Oyo

Table 2: Summary of Linear Regression Analysis Showing the impact of teachers’ teaching experience on students’ performance in Mathematics in secondary school in Oyo Town

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1434.910	1	1434.910	103.402	.000
	Residual	2386.810	172	13.877		
	Total	3821.720	173			

a. Dependent Variable: performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), teachers’ teaching experience

From the table above, since significance value $p < 0.05$, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis that there is significant impact of teachers’ teaching experience on students’ performance in Mathematics in secondary school in Oyo

Town. H₀3: There is no significant combine impact of teachers’ teachers’ quality and teaching experience on students’ performance in Mathematics in secondary school in Oyo town, Oyo State, Nigeria.

Table 3: Summary of Multiple Regression Analysis Showing the combine impact of teachers' quality and teaching experience on students' performance in Mathematics in secondary school in Oyo Town

Sources of Variance	Sum of Square	Df	Mean square	F	Significant
Regression	1860.227	2	930.114	81.084	0.000
Residue	1961.494	171	11.471		
Total	3821.721	173			

R = 0.703^a
 R Square = 0.494
 Adjusted R Square = 0.492
 Std. Error of the Estimate = 2.267

a. Dependent Variable: performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), teachers' teachers' quality and teaching experience

The table 3 indicated that the combine impact of teachers' quality and teaching experience on students' performance in Mathematics in secondary school in Oyo Town ($F_{(2,171)} = 375.645$; $Adj R^2 = 0.703$; $p < 0.05$). This implies that when teachers' teachers' quality and teaching experience were taken together, they jointly predict students' academic performance. The table further revealed that

multiple regression coefficient ($R = 0.703$) and multiple regression adjusted ($R^2 = 0.494$). This indicated that 49% of the variation in students' performance was accounted for by the combine contribution of teachers' quality and teaching experience while the remaining 51% is due to other factors and residuals not in this model.

Discussion

The findings revealed a significant impact of teacher's quality on the academic performance of students in Mathematics. This suggests that the quality of teachers, encompassing their knowledge, skills, and attitudes, plays a crucial role in determining students' outcomes in Mathematics. This aligns with existing literature, such as Abu and Fabunmi (2025) and Patrick (2025), which found that teacher's quality is a crucial factor in a student's performance. More so, studies have shown that teachers with strong subject matter knowledge and pedagogical skills tend to have a positive impact on student learning (Abu, & Fabunmi, 2025).

better equipped to manage classrooms, convey complex concepts, and adapt to individual student needs, ultimately leading to improve a student's performance. This corroborates research by Daso, (2023) and Tella (2024), who highlighted the importance of teacher's experience in impactive teaching. Experienced teachers can draw upon their wealth of knowledge and skills to create engaging lessons, address students' misconceptions, and foster a positive learning environment.

Furthermore, the study found a significant impact of teachers' experience on academic performance of students in Mathematics. This implies that teachers with more experience are

Interestingly, the study also revealed a combined impact of teacher's quality and experience on academic performance of students in Mathematics. This suggests that the interplay between teacher's quality and experience is a critical factor in determining students' outcomes. When teachers possess both strong knowledge of subject matter and

extensive experience, they are better positioned to provide high-quality instruction that meets the diverse needs of students. This is consistent with research that emphasizes the importance of teachers' factors in students' performance (Abu, & Fabunmi, 2025).

Conclusion

This study examined the quality of teachers and their teaching experiences on students' academic performance in Mathematics in Secondary schools in Oyo Town. The results showed that students' performance was significantly impacted by teacher quality and teaching experience. The findings highlight how crucial it is to fund teachers' preparation and professional growth in order to raise students' accomplishments. Educational stakeholders could significantly boost students' performance in Mathematics and other subjects by placing a high premium on both the quality and experience of Mathematics teachers.

Recommendations

Consequent upon the findings of this study, the following recommendations were hereby made:

1. Regular training and workshops for teachers to enhance their knowledge of subject matter and pedagogical skills should be organized by the government and they should be encouraged to pursue professional certifications and advanced degrees.
2. Government should implement strategies to retain experienced Mathematics teachers, vis-a-vis competitive salaries, incentives, and opportunities for career advancement.
3. School Administration should prioritize teacher's quality and experience when making hiring decisions and allocating resources to

improve teacher working conditions and student learning environments.

References

- Abu, P.B. & Fabunmi, M. (2025). The relationship among teacher variables and adult learners' academic performance. *International Journal of African American Studies*, 4 (1), 12-20
- Adaramola, S. A. & Obomamu, B. J. (2018). Impact of teacher's quality on the academic impactiveness of students in Rivers State universities. *International Journal of Innovative Education Research*, 10(3), 30-39.
- Adebayo, A. A. & Sayaya, S. S. (2023). Impact of teacher characteristics on students' academic performance among secondary schools. *Journal of Education and Practice* 4(3), 76 - 82
- Agwanda, J. A. (2025). Student, teacher and school environment factors as determinants of performance in senior secondary school chemistry in Oyo state, Nigeria. *The Journal of International Social Research*, 1(2), 13 - 34
- Akpo, E. A. & Jita, T. J. (2023). Teacher qualification and students' academic performance in science Mathematics and technology subjects in Kenya. *International Journal of Educational Administration and Policy Studies*. 7(3), 83 – 89
- Ali, M. A., Tela, A. T. & Saleh, S. S. (2020) Impactiveness of science, technology society and traditional science teaching methods on students' performance in Yola town, Adamawa state. *Research in Curriculum*. 5(1), 11 – 17.
- Asikhia, O. A. (2020). The impacts of teachers' qualifications on students' performance in Mathematics. *Sky Journal of Educational Research* 2(1), 010 - 014
- Daso, P.O. (2023). Teacher variables and senior secondary students' achievement in Mathematics in Rivers State, Nigeria. *European Scientific Journal*, 9 (10), 271-289.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014). Nigeria national policy on education (Revised Edition). NERC. Yaba Lagos.
- Lydia, A. L. & Joash, J. J. (2024). Teachers and students' academic performance in Nigerian secondary schools: Implication for planning. *Florida Journal of Educational Administration & Policy* 3(2), 86 – 103
- Nwachuckwu, I. N. (2022) Science teacher qualification and students' performance in secondary schools in Kano state. *Journal of Science Teacher Association of Nigeria*, 26(2), 24 – 51.
- Oyedeji, G. A. (2020). *The impact of school resources on the learning of inter-city children*. Balinger

Patrick, D. P. (2025) Validation of a modified Siegel's cognitive style test among Nigerian secondary school pupils. *African Journal of educational research* 3,142-143

Piaro, A. P. (2024). Status and Commitment of Teachers' Human Resources to Mathematics Teaching in Ogun State Secondary Schools. *The African Symposium*, 8(2), 159-166.

Usman, K. O. & Sabitu, K. A. (2025). Home environment, learning style and academic performance of secondary school students in Mathematics in Oyo Town, Oyo State, Nigeria. *World Journal of Educational Studies*, 3 (1), 2025, 16-21.

Tella, A. (2024). The impact of motivation on students' academic performance and learning outcomes in Mathematics among secondary school students in Nigeria. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science & Technology Education*, 3(2), 149-156.

Weiner, R. W. (022). What is relationship between teacher quality and student performance? An exploratory study. *Journal of Perspective Evaluation Education*, 20, 165 – 184.